

**ONLINE DATABASES AND UTILIZATION OF INFORMATION RESOURCES
BY POST-GRADUATES STUDENTS IN THE UNIVERSITY
OF CROSS RIVER STATE, CALABAR, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between online databases and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students in the university of Cross River State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were used to guide the study. Literature review was done accordingly. Accidental sampling technique was used for the study. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from a sample of 150 postgraduate students. Data analysis was done using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient statistic. The findings of the study showed that AGORA and HINARI significantly relate with utilization of information resources by postgraduate students. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that; the university management should ensure that the e-library section of the library has robust internet connection and adequate power supply to enhance full delivery of digitized online resources within the university and that the library management should subscribe to online databases for use by postgraduate students and faculty alike to boost their academic and research pursuit.

Keywords: Online databases, Utilization, Information Resources, Postgraduate students, Nigeria

Introduction

The effectiveness of any library is dependent on its resources and how they are used, as library information resources are acknowledged as crucial instruments in any college or university library (Nwosu & Opara, 2019). Information resources are seen as raw materials that provide crucial services for teaching, learning, and research processes. To meet the information demands of the patrons, both print and non-print information materials are acquired. Consistent online database running and subscriptions are essential to improve the effective and efficient use of these resources.

The use of online databases is dependent on postgraduate students' attitudes. Those who have a positive attitude toward using online databases will be more efficient and effective in their research, contribute significantly to their studies, stay up to date on the skills required to use the information resources, and positively impact their learning outcomes. To utilize is to make use of something, which is also known as finding a practical or effective use for something. Use alone refers to putting something into action or providing a service for

a specific objective (Egbe, & Ogunjimi, 2024; Toner, 2008). Therefore, using or putting to use information found in online databases is the simplest definition of using online databases. An individual may be called a user if they use something somewhere to accomplish their goals. In the light of this, postgraduate students who utilize web databases for their own academic or personal gains ought to be considered information resource consumers.

It has been observed that online databases are an essential component of resources for teaching, learning, and research. These tools and services have the potential to improve personality development and help people become proficient in their line of work if used appropriately. Scholars and students rely on pertinent library information resources to make significant progress in their research projects and academic advancement in general in an academic setting where advancement is contingent upon the availability and accessibility of current and pertinent information (Bokoh, Ajiboye & Bello, 2023). It is impossible to overstate how crucial it is to make sure that online databases are sufficiently and pertinently available to the university community in general and postgraduate students in particular. Therefore, it is necessary to make sure that online databases are sufficiently and effectively available in order to improve pertinent and well-structured information resources for convenient access, retrieval, and optimal use, ultimately meeting the information needs of postgraduate students.

A database is a sizable, frequently updated file of digital data pertaining to a particular topic or field. It is administered with the help of a database management system (DBMS) and consists of entries in a standard format that are arranged to facilitate and expedite search and retrieval. Database types range from general to specific (Olibie, Agu & Uzochina, 2015). Online databases are now a vital source of information that has improved the caliber of student research projects, (Sinh & Nhung, 2016). Because of their abundance of scholarly materials, academic libraries have long promoted the use of scholarly databases. They also give undergraduate and graduate students access to online databases to aid in their study (Mbabu, Bertram & Varnum, 2017). Online databases give postgraduate students a way to look for academic material, including many journals in certain fields that are available online.

Higher education institutions commonly maintain subscriptions to online databases to support student research initiatives. The consortium of Nigerian University Libraries (NULIB) has subscribed to several internet portals, including Global Online Research in Agriculture (AGORA), Health Internetwork Access to Research Initiatives (HINARI), Online Access to Research in the Environment (OARE), and the Database of African Theses and Dissertations (DATAD), as well as various offline databases such as MEDLINE and EBSCO-host, highlighting the importance of online databases (Anunobi & Okoye, 2018). Academic library gateways facilitate electronic access to global information resources. Online databases consist of interconnected digital information related to general knowledge or specific subject areas, systematically organized to enhance information retrieval via the internet or online networks, (Khan & Haridasan, 2015). Online databases are electronic collections of information accessible through the internet, typically comprising journal articles or references to those articles. There is significant interest among academics and information professionals in online databases.

Public wealth is now derived from online information sources. They are concrete tools for sharing knowledge in the humanities, sciences, and technology. Online databases are a wealth of information that libraries offer to help its users with their information needs. There are different kinds of online databases, including multimedia, full-text, bibliographic, and directory databases (Larson, 2017). The different kinds of online databases as identified by Atakan (2017), include EBSCO-host, AGORA, HINARI, DATAD, and EMERALDINSIGHT.COM. Online information resources include things like searchable databases, student-focused websites, internet search engines, electronic journals, news,

textbooks, government information, internet information, email services, and restricted library publications. All of these resources are available online.

Statement of the problem

The relevance of online databases in education generally and in postgraduate students works particularly, cannot be overemphasized. Postgraduate students in Nigerian universities cannot ignore the important role played by online databases in the provision of information resources for research and academic work. Observation by the researchers showed that postgraduate students in the study area are not making use of the available online databases for their research work, and other academic activities like assignment, homework and seminars, thereby, rendering these resources underutilized.

The researchers also observed that, despite the effort(s) of the university management in the provision of standard ICT facilities and services in the electronic library, and creation of awareness in regards to the provision of online databases, postgraduate students still are not making adequate use of these online databases, as such rendering the available online databases underutilized. This situation is worrisome, in the sense that, if not look into, may not only hinder or be a barrier to the mission and vision of the University, but will bring about the reduction in the standard of students' academic performance, as well as render the students incompetent. It is on this note that the researchers embarked on this study in order to find out the relationship between online databases and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students in the University of Cross River state, Calabar, Cross River State.

Objectives of the study

The study was conducted based on the following objectives.

1. To investigate the relationship between AGORA and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students.
2. To investigate the relationship between HINARI and the use of information resources by postgraduate students.

Research questions

This study generated the following research questions based on its objectives.

1. To what extent does AGORA relate to the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students?
2. What is the relationship between HINARI and the utilization of information resources among postgraduate students?

Statement of Hypotheses

The hypotheses presented below were formulated based on the study's objectives.

1. There is no significant relationship between AGORA and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students.
2. There is no significant relationship between HINARI and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students.

Review of related literature

AGORA and utilization of information resources

AGORA provides public organizations in poor countries with complimentary or low-cost access to essential scientific literature in agriculture and related biological, environmental, and social sciences. AGORA, launched in October 2003, provides users with access to more than 3000 papers from leading academic publishers globally. AGORA, led by the UN Food and Agriculture Organization, seeks to bolster food security by improving the quality and effectiveness of agricultural research, education, and training in low-income countries.

AGORA delivers superior, prompt, and pertinent agricultural information online to researchers, policymakers, educators, students, technical personnel, and extension specialists (FAO, 2022).

Olibie, Agu, and Uzoechina (2017), posited that by offering free or inexpensive access to resources, the Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture (AGORA) program seeks to raise the caliber and efficacy of agricultural research, instruction, and training in low- and middle-income nations. AGORA is part of Research4Life, a public-private collaboration involving Yale and Cornell Universities, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), and other entities. The authors emphasized that AGORA offers access to about 6,000 peer-reviewed publications and nearly 22,000 e-books. Additionally, the authors listed the following organizations as eligible to register for AGORA: local non-governmental organizations, government offices, national libraries, professional schools, research institutes, national universities, and agricultural extension centers (Olibie, Agu, & Uzoechina, 2017).

Otubelu and Leonard (2015), carried out a study on “the awareness and use of the Agora e-resources database by agricultural undergraduate students at Ebonyi State University Abakaliki, Nigeria”. Determining the degree and frequency of use of the current AGORA online services was one of the stated goals. A survey research design was used for the investigation. 160 people were chosen by simple random sampling, and the primary tool for gathering data was a questionnaire. The raw data that was gathered was subjected to descriptive statistics using Microsoft Excel. In the data analysis procedures, factors of research relevance were compared and contrasted using tables and pie charts. The results demonstrated that the current AGORA online tools are not being used very often (46%) because the relevant stakeholders are not well-informed about them.

Badiru (2015), conducted a study to find out “how final-year undergraduate students at the University of Ibadan's Faculty of Agriculture and Forestry used Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture” (AGORA). Using a basic random selection technique, 140 respondents in all were chosen from the faculty's eight departments. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the data, and at $P=0.05$, both descriptive (frequency, percentage, and averages) and inferential (Chi-square and PPMC) statistics were used to analyze the results. According to the findings, there is a strong correlation between AGORA and information resource use ($r = 0.334$; $p = 0.05$). It was suggested that more publicity is necessary to promote a shift in mindset and enhance students' use of AGORA. According to Dadzie's (2016) study on AGORA resources: Access and usage at Ashesi University College, the most significant limitation was an erratic power supply (64.3%), which was followed by students' inadequate orientation on AGORA use (55.0%). The fact that 19.3% of people are unaware about AGORA is not a significant barrier because awareness is the primary prerequisite for use. The institution must take some concrete action by setting up training sessions and seminars to teach students how to use AGORA and address the issue of erratic power supply.

In a study conducted by Abubakar and Akpor (2017), to investigate “how agricultural scientists use online databases and information resources for research in federal university libraries in North Central Nigeria”, it was found that 57.9% of the respondents had never looked for journals on AGORA. Only 4.3% have written on AGORA, majority (80.7%) of the respondents have never taken part in an AGORA group discussion, indicating that students in the study area are not using AGORA to its full potential. It was also discovered that the limited utilization of AGORA's components may have resulted from improper awareness of its additional uses. Therefore, in order to promote full utilization, further awareness-raising regarding the components of AGORA should be done.

Maibeni and Dash (2023) conducted a study on the comprehension and utilization of internet databases by postgraduate students at Federal University Kashere, Gombe. One of the aims was to ascertain the relationship between AGORA and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data, and a questionnaire was deployed to gather information from 107 participants in the study, which adopted the survey research approach. The study's findings revealed a significant association between AGORA and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students. To ascertain the disparity between the availability and underutilization of these databases, it was recommended that the school administration, via its library and ICT centers, perform needs assessments of all subscribed databases and survey postgraduate students' information requirements. To enhance the use of online databases, the library website should incorporate an abstract for each database along with the subjects it encompasses. This will attract further users.

HINARI and utilization of information resources

One of four Research4Life (R4L) initiatives is HINARI Access to Research in Health. The World Health Organization (WHO), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), Cornell and Yale Universities, the International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers, and more than 200 international scientific publishers are participating in R4L as a public-private partnership (Research4Life, 2016). R4L was established to provide free or inexpensive access to essential scientific knowledge in order to close a large knowledge gap in developing nations. HINARI was the first R4L initiative with a focus on health research. Although that name has been dropped, the acronym stands for Health Inter-Network Access to Research Initiative. The other R4L initiatives concentrate on development and innovation, agriculture, and environmental research. To evaluate R4L initiatives and their impact on developing nations' involvement in the international research community, the R4L partners carried out an infrastructure and user experience study in 2010 (Gaible, Gedye, Ochs, Parker & Rudgard, 2016).

Gaible et al, (2016), stated that the user experience review's findings supported the notion that R4L programs are highly beneficial to their users; nevertheless, they also showed that "limited awareness" of and "difficulties in finding relevant information" hindered the best possible use of these products. Using regional and national platforms whenever feasible, the R4L partners established "networks among communities of practice" as one of their institutional level efforts in response to these findings. Over the past ten years, HINARI has developed into a virtual learning hub that has demonstrated the capacity to close the information gap worldwide. Researchers in developing nations currently use it as one of their main gateways, and publishers have promised to continue supporting it through 2020 (R4L, 2016). HINARI is currently run by a small group of people who have collaborated and worked proactively to build a strong program basis. Determining how the success attained thus far can be maintained and increased is crucial as the program grows. This commentary suggests strategies to raise awareness and provide usage training for HINARI through networks within the National Library of Medicine (NLM) and the Medical Library Association (MLA) (R4L, 2016).

Using an anonymous, standardized questionnaire, Dahiru (2021) carried out a cross-sectional survey to evaluate how doctors in Ibadan, Nigeria, use the HINARI database to obtain health information for patient care. According to the survey, just 7% of respondents had ever looked for the Cochrane Library, but 98% of respondents had used HINARI and 76% accessed it on CyberCape. Of the 99% of respondents, Medline/PubMed was the most searched resource. Additionally, the survey discovered that 58.1% of participants felt uneasy

about downloading full-text papers from websites like the Health Internet Access to Research Initiative (HINARI). The respondents' inability to access broadband internet, lack of knowledge about search techniques, access fees, and passwords were the main obstacles to using the HINARI database. Collaboration has attempted to make its evaluations freely available and accessible to developing nations; nevertheless, the format is likely difficult, and RCTs typically examine illnesses and therapies that may not be as pertinent to the developing world (Davies, 2011).

Ajuwon and Olorunsaye (2016), opined that the developing world now has free or extremely inexpensive access to up to 14,000 online journals and 46,000 e-books in biomedical and related social sciences thanks to the World Health Organization's (WHO) work on Health Internet Access to Research Initiatives (HINARI) and its partnership with major publishers. However, many underdeveloped nations, like Pakistan, are not able to use this free or extremely inexpensive access to HINARI. Obstacles that both rural and non-rural primary care doctors must overcome. The nations that have access to this network are the ones that they consult while looking for health information. It was suggested that information outreach programs be implemented in Pakistan's rural areas to encourage the usage, access, and exchange of information.

One thousand, one hundred and fifty (1150) clinicians and researchers from 12 tertiary healthcare facilities in southwest Nigeria that had access to HINARI participated in a descriptive cross-sectional survey that was carried out by Ajuwon and Olorunsaye (2015). According to the study, the majority (72.0%) knew about HINARI, used its resources the most, and reported that the biggest obstacle to accessing it was a lack of a password. According to Anwar and Shammim (2011), a large number of students and healthcare professionals are still utterly ignorant about HINARI and are therefore unable to utilize its information resources to their full potential. According to several studies, most researchers and doctors in Nigerian healthcare facilities use HINARI extensively (Anyaku & Anunobi, 2015). The study came to the conclusion that if the findings are put into practice, the issue of poor Research4life database utilization among universities and research institutes in underdeveloped nations may eventually be resolved.

Inozemtzeva, Kirsanova, Troufanova, and Semenova (2018) examined databases and the utilization of information resources by Malaysian medical students. The study employed a survey research design as its methodological approach. The research utilized a stratified random sampling method. The principal instrument employed for data collection was a questionnaire, and the study's subjects comprised final-year medical students from Malaysian University. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data. The results demonstrated a robust association between HINARI and the utilization of information resources by medical students at the University of Malaysia. This means that robust utilization of online databases can help students achieve academic excellence.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design. The research was conducted at the University of Cross River State. The study population comprised one hundred and fifty-five (155) postgraduate students. The complete population of the study served as the sample for the research. The study employed an accidental sampling technique. A systematic questionnaire was employed to gather data from the participants. Of the one hundred fifty-five questionnaires distributed, only one hundred and fifty were deemed legitimate and utilized for the study. The gathered data were analyzed utilizing the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistic.

Presentation of results

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between AGORA and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students. The independent variable in this hypothesis is AGORA while the dependent variable is utilization of information resources. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient statistical analysis was employed to test the hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Pearson's product moment coefficient for the relationship between AGORA and utilization of information resources (N=150)

Variable	X	SD	r-value	p-value
AGORA	21.18	2.11	.453*	0.406
Utilization of Information resources by postgraduate students	20.13	.78		

*Significant at 0.05 level, df = 148; critical r-value = 0.406

The results in table 1 above showed that the “calculated r-value of .453 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.406 at 0.05 level of significance with 148 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between AGORA and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students is rejected therefore the alternative hypothesis was retained”. This means that there is a significant relationship between AGORA and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students in the University of Cross River State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between HINARI and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students. The independent variable in this hypothesis is HINARI while the dependent variable is utilization of information resources. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient statistical analysis was employed to test the hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Pearson's product moment coefficient for the relationship between HINARI and utilization of information resources (N=150)

Variable	X	SD	r-value	p-value
HINARI	23.17	2.17	.479*	0.413
Utilization of Information resources by postgraduate students	22.51	.77		

*Significant at 0.05 level, df = 148; critical r-value = 0.413

The results in table 2 above showed that the “calculated r-value of .479 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.413 at 0.05 level of significance with 148 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between HINARI and utilization of information resources is rejected therefore the alternative

hypothesis was retained”. This means that HINARI significantly relate with utilization of information resources by postgraduate students in the University of Cross River State.

Discussion of findings

AGORA and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students.

The findings of this hypothesis indicated a substantial correlation between AGORA and the use of information resources by postgraduate students at the University of Cross River State. This indicates that postgraduate students utilizing the AGORA database are likely to excel in both research and academic performance. This conclusion aligns with the findings of Olibie, Agu, and Uzoechina (2017), who determined that the Global Online Research in Agriculture (AGORA) program seeks to enhance the quality and efficacy of agricultural research, education, and training in low and middle-income countries by offering complimentary or affordable access to resources. AGORA is an initiative of Research4Life, a public-private collaboration involving the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Cornell University, Yale University, and more entities.

HINARI and utilization of information resources by postgraduate students.

The findings of this hypothesis indicated a substantial correlation between HINARI and the utilization of information resources by postgraduate students at the University of Cross River State. The utilization of HINARI by postgraduate students can beneficially impact their academic pursuits. This discovery aligns with the research undertaken by Inozemtzeva, Kirsanova, Troufanova, and Semenova (2018), which examined databases and the consumption of information resources among medical students in Malaysia. The findings indicated a substantial link between HINARI and the consumption of information resources among medical students at the University of Malaysia.

Conclusion and recommendation

Online databases can be accessed from anywhere with an internet connection, making them ideal for remote work and collaboration, they provide a convenient and efficient way to manage and access information over the internet, with various applications in different fields of study. Postgraduate students and other researchers including faculty can exploit this opportunity to boost their research productivity. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that;

1. The University management should ensure that the e-library section of the library has robust internet connection and adequate power supply to enhance full delivery of digitized online resources within the University.
2. The library management should subscribe to online databases for use by postgraduate students and faculty alike to boost their academic and research pursuit.

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